

DEFORMATION MECHANISMS IN FABRIC REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties of composites based on warp knitted (non-crimp) fabrics are superior to conventional textile systems (e.g. woven fabrics) and close to those of unidirectional prepreg tape laminates, largely due to the elimination of fibre crimp. Furthermore, reinforcement architecture has been linked with the nature of damage development during impact loading. Fracture mechanisms on a microstructural level may be influenced by the route of composite manufacture.

Introduction

In the commercial aerospace industry metallic materials are increasingly being superseded by carbon fibre reinforced plastics to reduce weight. It was expected that the high cost of unidirectional prepreg tape could be offset by manufacturing cost reductions from parts integration and automation. However, the problem of poor transverse properties gives rise to impact damage tolerance concerns. In addition excessively high laminating costs has provided an obstacle to the justification of new composite structure on economic grounds.

In recognition of the limitations imposed upon the design allowables for composites, new manufacturing techniques are being exploited to further reduce manufacturing costs and improve the damage tolerance of the resulting material system. To achieve this the industry is looking to textiles.

Textile processed composites have advantages over their unidirectional prepreg tape counterparts in that they can be highly automated, pre-fabricated to near net shapes with high volumes/through-put and provide the designer with greater flexibility through a wider range of processing routes e.g. RTM, RFI etc. thereby reducing manufacturing costs. In addition it has been recognised that the reinforcement architecture plays a key role in the determination and distribution of fracture mechanisms.

Through judicious use of the textile technique (reinforcement architecture) improvements in impact resistance and subsequent compression strength have been realised. It is through the rational exploitation of textile manufacturing methods that continued improvements in damage tolerance are likely to be achieved without undermining the undamaged mechanical properties of the component.

Materials and Testing

The class of material under investigation is a triaxial non-crimp fabric (NCF) which distinguishes itself from two dimensional weaves and full three dimensional constructions by utilising a secondary yarn that binds 'bundles' of differing orientations together forming a 'blanket' with near zero crimp, figure 1.

An equivalent construction was fabricated from unidirectional prepreg tape, $[45_2, -45_2, 0_6, -45_2, 45_2]_S$, to reflect the lay-up and mass distribution of the fibres in the non-crimp fabric.

The Ciba 914 resin was used for both material systems, which were processed using autoclave curing.

Basic mechanical testing was carried out to compare the performance of the non-crimp fabric in tension and compression with its equivalent unidirectional prepreg tape counterpart.

Impact and compression after impact was conducted on both material systems using a miniature test configuration developed at QMW¹. The specimens were impacted by a 3.96 kg mass using an in-house instrumented impact machine with CEAST software. In each instance the specimens were only struck once with a 20 mm hemisphere.

Results

Mechanical Properties

The in-plane mechanical properties of non-crimp fabric compared with the unidirectional prepreg composite previously described are given in Table 1.

The results indicate that for most mechanical properties, the NCF laminates are equivalent to the laminates based on UD prepreps. The only significant exception to this trend is the compression strengths of undamaged laminates in which a reduction of between 10-15% in compression strength was observed for NCF laminates compared to UD prepreg tape laminates. This effect is not unexpected and is linked to the fibre waviness², both in and out of plane that is observed in the NCF laminates.

Damage Tolerance

Impact induced fracture mechanisms in unidirectional prepreg tape constructions are well documented and typically consist of transverse cracks below the contact region with shear fractures that propagate to plies of differing orientation forming inplane fractures or, delaminations and this geometry forms the well defined 'cone' or 'pine tree' shape. The discrete nature of the delaminations between individual plies is well represented by time of flight C-scans of the damaged plate as shown in figure 2a.

The damage sustained by the non crimp fabric laminates was different. The C-scans, figure 2b show that cracking resembling delamination occurs but this is more diffuse. A micrograph showing a cross section through a typical NCF sample after impact shows a different cracking pattern to the cone of pine tree characteristic of the UD prepreg materials. In keeping with the botanical descriptions of impact induced fractures, the pattern observed in the non-crimp fabric may be more easily described as "root-like" figure 3.

Shear and transverse cracks are still in evidence, but are clearly influenced by the local fibre architecture. More specifically in some cases the path of a crack is determined by the presence of a fibre bundle. In other cases however the cracking seems to be irregular and to be completely unaffected not only by local fibre architecture but also by the presence of ply or layer boundaries. The microstructural features influencing crack growth are clearly complex but must include some weak planes around fibre bundles, with the action of a stitching yarn itself undefined.

The plan area extent of the cracking as viewed using a 2-D C-scan picture of the damage zone is compared for the UD-prepreg laminates and the NCF laminates in figure 4. Two sets of data are shown for each material type. In one case the extent of damage is measured along the major length of the material, corresponding to the direction of the 0 degree plies, while the second set corresponds to the width of the specimen, at 90 degrees to the 0 degree plies. The data is different

for each direction in both cases. Generally the extent of the cracking is greater along the outer layer fibre direction and there is a slight tendency for the UD-prepreg laminates to exhibit a greater crack extent in both orientations, particularly at the higher energy impacts.

The data for compression after impact is shown in figure 5. The data is presented as compression strength versus damage width to emphasise the resistance of propagation of the damage created during impact and to separate any effects due to a greater susceptibility to damage during impact itself³. In this instance the behaviour of both materials was similar to impact with if anything damage being formed slightly more easily in the UD prepreg laminates. The compression after impact data reveals little difference between the NCF and UD systems but again there is a slightly greater resistance to damage propagation with the NCF materials, particularly when loaded transverse to the outermost fibre layers.

Discussion

The observed inferior compression strength of the NCF materials, due to the presence of some fibre waviness, is however not so critical as the relative compression after impact performance of the two materials. The fact that the NCF materials if anything performed better than the UD prepreg equivalents despite the material being inherently weaker in this direction, reflects some superior resistance to the propagation of damage under compression loading with the NCF material. This is largely attributed to the nature of the damage formed during the impact test. The conventional UD prepreg tape laminates exhibited large, distinct delaminations which can have a significant local effect in triggering buckling of plies or buckling of the whole laminate. The diffuse nature of the damage formed in the NCF laminates suggest that individual large delaminations do not form, and as a consequence the local tendency to buckle is reduced. The uncracked zones around the scattered spots of damage or cracking, effectively act as tie bars holding the composite structure together.

The nature of the cracking pattern in the NCF is evidently influenced by the detailed fibre architectures. Cracking would appear to occur preferentially at or around fibre bundles, but these local cracks are restricted from coalescing to form a single large delamination by the presence of the stitching yarns and possibly by the directional and irregular nature of the crack surface that must form around the bundle. The cracks that grow at the interface of plies in a UD stack effectively grow in a flat plane and this does not provide much of a physical obstacle to growth in two dimensions. The crack that grows around a bundle surface is in contrast not flat and so growing perpendicular to the direction of the tow might be extremely difficult. This latter effect would operate irrespective of the presence of stitching yarns passing across the crack plane and might explain why the material appears tough and can exhibit high G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values even when cracks are grown between layers in the composite where no cross-layer stitching is present⁴.

Conclusion

The principal conclusion is that the nature of crack development under impact conditions in NCF based laminates is different to that developed in standard unidirectional prepreg tape based laminates.

The differences in the crack pattern appear to impart a slight improvement in damage tolerance in the materials when subsequently loaded in compression. This effect would appear to be more marked if undamaged compression strength is taken into account.

The general mechanical properties of NCF systems examined in this paper are otherwise equivalent to those of UD-based materials and this indicates that the textile route to composite parts production may not involve any significant compromise on the part of materials properties and subsequent weight penalties for aerospace structures.

Table 1 Mechanical Properties of the NCF and UD Prepreg Tape

Tension	NCF	UD Prepreg Tape
Modulus (GPa)	64.8 (2.1)	61.6 (0.7)
Strength (MPa)	687 (0.9)	710 (3.1)
Compression		
Modulus (GPa)	56.9 (0.8)	52.6 (0.5)
Strength (MPa)	636 (3.0)	716 (2.1)

Coefficient of variation given in brackets

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References

1. **Hogg, P.J., Prichard, J.C. and Stone, D.L.** A miniature post-impact compression test *ECCM-CTS Sept 1992 Netherlands, pp 357-370, Pub EACM Bordeaux 1992.*
2. **Farley, G.L. and Dickinson, L.C.** Removal of surface loop from stitched composites can improve compression and coompression-after-impact strengths *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites Vol 11 No. 6 1992, pp 633-642.*
3. **Bibo, G.A., Hogg, P.J and Kemp, M.** Damage tolerance of UD prepreg tape and textile reinforced glass epoxy *3rd International Conference on Deformation and Fracture of Composites, March 1995, Surrey.*
4. **Backhouse, R., Blakeman, C. and Irving, P.E.** Mechanisms of toughness enhancement in carbon fibre non crimp fabric composites *3rd International Conference on Deformation and Fracture of Composites, March 1995, Surrey.*

Figure 1. Schematic idealisation of the construction of multi-axial (non-crimp) fabrics.

Figure 3. Optical micrograph of the fracture mechanisms induced in the NCF by low energy impacts.

Figure 2a. Distribution of delamination using time of flight C-scan for UD prepreg tape.

Figure 2b. Distribution of fractures using time of flight C-scan for the NCF.

Figure 4. Impact induced damage extent vs impact energy for the NCF and UD prepreg tape.

Figure 5. Compression-after-impact strength vs damage extent for the NCF and UD prepreg tape.